

3D network of MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite studied by Raman spectroscopy

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This paper is dedicated to the memory of our dear co-worker and friend Hańcza Barbara Surma, who passed away while this manuscript was being completed.

ABSTRACT

A MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite grown by the micro-pulling down method was studied by Raman spectroscopy. The Raman investigation confirmed that this eutectic consists of the three-dimensional network of TiO₂ elongated precipitates interconnected by thin TiO₂ lamellas

embedded in a MnTiO_3 matrix. Raman scattering spectra revealed that the TiO_2 phase crystallizes in the rutile structure and the MnTiO_3 matrix in the ilmenite structure. The thin lamella regions combine both the TiO_2 and MnTiO_3 phases. Two Raman lines at 116 cm^{-1} and 136 cm^{-1} not observed in a perfect ilmenite single crystal but observed for the eutectic MnTiO_3 phase can be used to derive information about deviations in the MnTiO_3 structure.

Keywords: MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 , eutectic composite, MnTiO_3 single crystal, TiO_2 single crystal, Raman spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

Composite materials are increasingly attracting the interest of the scientific community because of their unique properties and numerous potential applications. Eutectic materials are a special kind of composites where, from a completely mixable melt a two-phase solid is obtained through a cooperative growth which results in self-organized micro/nanostructures. Eutectic metal-metal alloys are broadly used in everyday life due to their superior mechanical properties; however other eutectic compositions have been studied recently, such as oxide-oxide and metal-oxide. The examples of proposed applications include metamaterials [1–4], plasmonic materials [5–7] photonic crystals [8,9], solid-oxide fuel cells [10,11], photoelectrochemistry [12–14], scintillators [15,16] and others. Their unique properties result from the combination of two phases; sharp interfaces; unique micro/nanostructures with controllable dimensions; and the possibility of demonstration of both additive as well as product properties. While the additive properties originate from the constituent eutectic phases, the product properties originate from the interaction between them [17].

MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 eutectic composite [18] has been recently studied and its potential as a photocatalytic material in both the UV and visible region has been envisaged, due to the two

photocatalytic phases. TiO_2 is a well-known material which has been used as a pigment for centuries [19].

It is a semiconductor with a band gap of ~ 3 eV [20–23] and it is used as photocatalyst [24]. However, its wide band gap only allows absorption of UV radiation and therefore needs to be reduced by doping in order to inexpensively remove water pollution. Moreover, TiO_2 may be used to produce solar cells [25]; in gas sensing devices [26]; and in electrochemistry [27]. MnTiO_3 is a semiconductor and antiferromagnetic material (below $T_N=64.2$ K) [28,29]. Therefore its envisaged potential applications include integrated circuit devices [29]; gas and humidity sensors [30]; and non-linear optics [28]. Thanks to high capacity and good cycling stability MnTiO_3 became a promising material for lithium-ion-based batteries [31]. As it was recently published, due to the minimized toxicity manganese titanate nanosheets were used as substrates for enzymes for programmed tumor-killing [32]. Moreover, MnTiO_3 is a visible light photocatalyst [33] with a band gap of 2.4-3 eV [20,29,34,35].

The potential synergy of TiO_2 and MnTiO_3 materials comes from their properties and can be applied in catalysis [36], electroceramics [37], energy storage [38].

The above facts indicate that $\text{MnTiO}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ eutectic composite constitutes an extremely promising material that should be studied. Despite Raman spectroscopy being a powerful method to characterize materials, to our knowledge, published Raman studies of eutectic composites are very limited and papers concerning $\text{MnTiO}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ eutectic material are scarce [18,39]. Therefore, a Raman spectroscopic study of the above-mentioned eutectic composite is the main aim of this work.

2. Experimental section

The MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 eutectic composite as well as TiO_2 and MnTiO_3 crystals were grown by the micro-pulling-down method at the Łukasiewicz Research Network – Institute of Microelectronics and Photonics. High purity raw material powders, MnO (99.99%) and TiO_2 (99.99%) were carefully weighted in a MnO 43 mol.% - TiO_2 57 mol.% molar ratio according to the phase diagram presented in Fig. 1a [40] and placed in an iridium crucible. All fibers were grown using an yttrium-aluminium garnet seed in nitrogen atmosphere (1 atm.) with 0.15 mm/min pulling rate. The eutectic point temperature for MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 is 1370 °C. The heat was controlled by the generator's power which depends on the applied thermal system. In case of TiO_2 and MnTiO_3 single crystals the pulling rates were 0.5 and 0.05 mm/min, respectively. More details concerning producing eutectic composites with the micro-pulling down method are given elsewhere [18,39]. The as-grown rods of MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 composite as well as TiO_2 and MnTiO_3 crystals have black coloration (Fig. 1b,c,d). For the studies the eutectic samples were cut perpendicular to the growth direction, and its cross-sections were examined with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and with Raman spectroscopy.

Fig. 1. MnO-TiO₂ system phase diagram (a), obtained samples: (b) TiO₂ crystal, (c) as-grown MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite, and (d) MnTiO₃ single crystal.

Room temperature Raman experiments were carried out with HORIBA's LabRam HR Evolution & Photoluminescence spectrometer available at the University of Warsaw. The helium-neon laser line of 633 nm was used as the excitation. The beam was focused to a spot size of 0.86 μm with a 100x/0.9 objective lens. Raman mapping was done by moving the stage in 1 μm increments over an approximate area of 60x70 μm^2 . Experiments were conducted with a back scattering geometry. The laboratory coordinate system was chosen in such a way that the crystal surface normal to the sample, as well as incident and scattered beam coincided with Z axis. The laser beam (LB) was polarized (LP) in such way that electric vector was parallel to Y (vertical) or X (horizontal) axis on the sample surface for 0° and 90° polarization, respectively and for the sample orientation shown in Fig.2a. The Raman signal (RS) was collected for p (Y) and s (X) polarization (RP). The schedule LB(LP RP)RS was used for the labelling the experiment setup configuration : Z(XX)Z, Z(YY)Z, Z(XY)Z and Z(YX)Z .

3. Results and Discussion

Based on our previous studies including powder X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and high-resolution transmission electron microscopy it has been shown that the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite consists of a three-dimensional network of TiO₂ elongated precipitates ellipsoidal in the cross-section, interconnected by thin TiO₂ lamellas all embedded in the MnTiO₃ matrix. The ellipsoidal precipitations grow in the [001] orientation while lamellas grow in the [010] crystallographic direction[18].

In Fig. 2a the image of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic cross-section is shown. Three observed distinct regions are labeled A, B and C. According to SEM [18] the A and B regions correspond

to the TiO_2 phase, while the C region corresponds to the MnTiO_3 phase. Results of Raman spectroscopy experiments for the MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 eutectic composite in comparison with the crystals of rutile TiO_2 [001] and ilmenite MnTiO_3 are shown in Fig. 2b, while a Raman characteristic frequencies map corresponding to the optical image is shown in Fig. 2c. The labelled lines in figure 2c are the lines that were used as the phase markers for TiO_2 (green area) and MnTiO_3 (red area) and for high frequency modes related to contaminants (blue area).

The spectrum measured for region “A” has a pronounced bands at 142, 445, 611 cm^{-1} and a wide band at 238 cm^{-1} . The observed spectra for the regions “C” and “B” resemble the one for ilmenite MnTiO_3 . The presence of some additional lines in the spectral regions 950-970 cm^{-1} and 1370-1405 cm^{-1} has been reported before: these high-energy lines may be the result of surface oxygen contaminants (OH, CO and CO_2) [41]. Such contaminants are especially seen in the B region which contains two interfaces, which is why it is potentially more susceptible to contain e.g. traces of the polishing materials.

Fig. 2. Raman spectra for MnTiO_3 - TiO_2 eutectic composite in comparison with spectra for MnTiO_3 and TiO_2 crystals. (a) Optical image of the eutectic composite microstructure. (b)

Raman spectra. (c) Raman spectral image, for the TiO₂ marker at 445cm⁻¹ (green area) and for the MnTiO₃ marker at 334 cm⁻¹ (red area) and 1408 cm⁻¹ (blue area).

TiO₂ may crystallize in three different structures (rutile, anatase and brookite) [42,43]. However following our previous studies of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite we concentrated here on rutile, which crystallizes in a tetragonal crystal system in the P4₂/mm (D_{4h}) space group with the chemical formula repeated twice (Z=2) in the unit cell [44–47]. The Raman scattering spectra is therefore expected to have four active modes: A_{1g} + B_{1g} + B_{2g} + E_g. A and B are non-degenerate modes while E is doubly – degenerate. A and B are respectively symmetric and antisymmetric modes with respect to the highest-fold axis. 1 and 2 stands respectively for symmetric and antisymmetric modes with regards to the two-fold axis. While g stands for a symmetric mode with respect to the centre of symmetry.

Anatase TiO₂ crystallizes in a tetragonal system in space group I4₁/amd (D_{4h}), with Z=4 [45,46,48]. Raman spectra of anatase have six active modes. Brookite, on the other hand, crystallizes in an orthorhombic system in space group Pbc (D_{2h}) with Z=8, therefore its Raman spectra is more complicated and has at least 15 vibrational bands [38,45,46]. Thus Raman experiments allow us to distinguish between three possible structures of TiO₂ (rutile, anatase, brookite [42,49]). The MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite spectrum for region “A” is very similar to that of the rutile TiO₂ single crystal. The line at 445cm⁻¹ that is characteristic for the rutile TiO₂ Raman spectrum was used as a marker for this phase in the MnTiO₂-TiO₃ eutectic composite (Fig. 2c).

MnTiO₃ on the other hand, has an ilmenite structure with the trigonal crystal system $R\bar{3}$ (S6) space group and Z=6. Therefore one may expect 10 Raman active modes (5A_g+5E_g) [23,50–52]. The Raman spectra obtained at point “C” of the eutectic composite (Fig 2b) agree roughly

with the spectra measured for the MnTiO₃ single crystal (Table.2). The Raman line at 334 cm⁻¹ was used as a marker for MnTiO₃ phase in the eutectic composite (Fig. 2c).

For more precise analysis Lorentzian functions were used to deconvolute the Raman spectra and to determine intensities, frequencies and widths of particular lines. According to this model the intensity of a special line can be represented by:

$$I(\omega) = \sum_i \frac{A_i}{1 + (\omega - \omega_i)^2 / \gamma_i^2} \quad (1)$$

where A_i , ω_i and γ_i are amplitude, frequency and width of i-th line, respectively. Fitting results of the region "A" Raman spectra are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at region "A" of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. For clarity TiO_{2-x}N_x Raman lines are plotted in orange.

Table 1. Calculated frequencies, ω_i , line widths, γ_i , and possible assignment of phonon modes for region "A" of MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite and rutile TiO₂ crystal.

Phonon mode	Region "A"		Rutile TiO ₂ crystal		Pure rutile TiO ₂ Ref. [53]	TiO _{2-x} N _x nanorods Ref. [54]	Assignment
	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	ω_i	
A	141.7	1.3	142.3	1.01	143	148	B _{1g}
B	232.5	43.2	235.0	39.57	236	249	two-phonon process (TPP)
C	356.4	70.2	352.8	69.76		336	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
D	444.6	20.4	443.6	20.13	447	441	E _g
E	531.4	36.4	526.9	39.39		543	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
F	610.4	22.8	609.0	22.56	612	607	A _{1g}
G	687.2	46.5	706.3	33.70		689	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
H	787.3	46.9	828.8	24.64	826		B _{2g}
I	1371.2	15.9					OH/CO/CO ₂
J	1403.1	10.1					OH/CO/CO ₂

The position and linewidth of modes for TiO₂, especially the E_g mode at 447 cm⁻¹, are considered to be stoichiometry (O/Ti) sensitive [33,55,56]. All calculated mode frequencies of rutile TiO₂ show redshifts with respect to the reference pure rutile TiO₂ [53] which means there is a deficiency of oxygen in TiO₂ phase. The widths of most of the lines for the TiO₂ phase are close to the ones for rutile single crystals indicating homogeneity of the TiO₂ phase in the studied eutectic. Due to overlapping of the line H with the strongest lines G and F, the higher width of the B_{2g} mode can be due to the low precision of the deconvolution process.

Spectra for region "A", in addition to ordinary lines of rutile TiO₂, exhibit lines at 356, 531 and 687 cm⁻¹. While the observed shifts can be caused by minute amount of various dopants (including Mn atoms), such lines have been previously reported for nitrogen doped TiO_{2-x}N_x nanorods [54]. The presence of nitrogen might be expected in the studied eutectic composite as the growing process was carried in a nitrogen atmosphere and it is known that nitrogen forms N-Ti bonds with titanium [54]. According to previous reports [54,57,58], the bands at around 200cm⁻¹ 330cm⁻¹ 550cm⁻¹ are assigned to the first order and the band at 600-700cm⁻¹ to the second order scattering of nonstoichiometric TiN. For a 1:1 stoichiometry, perfect TiN crystal the first order Raman spectrum is forbidden. So the presence of these three broad bands (Fig. 3

– lines C,E,H) for the TiO₂ phase is assigned to the incorporation of nitrogen into the eutectic composite during the growth process and formation of Ti-N bonds.

The Raman spectrum for region C (Fig. 2a) fits the spectrum for the MnTiO₃ phase (Fig. 4 and Table 2). Labelling of the lines was done according to [59]. Deconvolution resulted in the appearance of the additional lines at about 116, 138.

The four vibrations A_{g(2)}, A_{g3}, E_{g2} and E_{g3} are related to O²⁻-Ti⁴⁺-O²⁻ bending motions and in fact represent the angles of different O²⁻-Ti⁴⁺-O²⁻ bonds. The A_{g4} and E_{g4} vibrations are assigned to the translations of the TiO₆ octahedra against Mn²⁺ cations; A_{g5} and E_{g5} to translations of the Mn²⁺ cation against the oxygen framework; and A_{g1} and E_{g1} to stretching of the Ti⁴⁺-O²⁻ bond [52]. The shift of the A_{g1} and E_{g1} vibrations to higher frequencies compared to the single crystals, which is observed for the MnTiO₃ phase, suggests some distortion of the TiO₆ octahedron [52]. The small band at around 514 cm⁻¹ also indicates a small amount of nitrogen atoms in this phase. Wider Raman lines for the MnTiO₃ phase in the eutectic composite than for single MnTiO₃ crystal reveal the presence of some disturbance in the lattice structure for this phase.

Fig. 4. Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at point C for MnTiO₃ phase in MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. Calculated parameters of the deconvoluted spectrum are gathered in Table 2.

Table 2. Calculated frequencies, ω_i , line widths, γ_i , and possible assignment of phonon modes for the regions "B" and "C" of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite and for MnTiO₃ and rutile TiO₂ crystals.

Phonon mode	Region "B"		Region "C"		MnTiO ₃ single crystal		MnTiO ₃ single crystal [60]		Rutile TiO ₂ single crystal		Assignment
	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	ω_i	γ_i		
1	96.1	11.6	116	10.2							unknown
2	133.5	17.6	138.6	11.4							unknown
3								142.3	1.01		B _{1g} (TiO ₂)
4	161.9	17.6	164.7	8.9	164.9	2.0	168				E _{g(5)} (MnTiO ₃)
5	203.8	17.6	202.4	10.2	202.5	2.4	202				A _{g(5)} (MnTiO ₃)
6	236.4	8.0	234.6	7.8	236.6	3.1	235				E _{g(4)} (MnTiO ₃)
7	259.2	110						235.0	39.6		TPP (TiO ₂)
8	266.7	11.6	261.3	13.8	263.9	4.1	264				A _{g(4)} (MnTiO ₃)
9	335.5	17.6	334.8	12.6	334.7	5.1	335				A _{g(3)} (MnTiO ₃)
10	362.4	8.6	358.5	12.6	359.4	3.3	360				E _{g(3)} (MnTiO ₃)

11	366.9	206.1							$E_{(g3)}$ (MnTiO ₃)
12	449.6	54.6	436.3	21			443.6	20.1	TiO ₂ /MnTiO ₃
13	514.0	51.6	514.6	56.0			526.9	39.4	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
14	612.3	60.3	609.4	45.4			609.0	22.6	$E_{(g1)}$ (MnTiO ₃)
15	687.7	43.9	683.5	30.8	685.0	9.3	682		$A_{(g1)}$ (MnTiO ₃)
16	712	124.0							TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
17	798.7	60.7					828.8	24.6	$B_{(2g)}$ (TiO ₂)
18	958.0	5.0							OH/CO/CO ₂
19	977.0	2.8							OH/CO/CO ₂
20	1377	15.9							OH/CO/CO ₂
21	1404.5	17.9							OH/CO/CO ₂

The Raman spectrum for the lamella (point B) that forms the interconnection of the two TiO₂ regions, presented in Fig. 5, shows spectral characteristic of both the TiO₂ and MnTiO₃ phases (Fig. 5 and Table 2). Three pronounced broad bands at around 330 cm⁻¹, 514 cm⁻¹ and 710 cm⁻¹, associated with the presence of the nitrogen, occur in the lamella region (Fig. 6b–green lines). There is nothing surprising that nitrogen introduced during growing process will locate itself preferentially at the most disturbed region.

Fig. 5 (a) Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at point B (lamella region) in the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. Calculated parameters of the deconvoluted spectrum are gathered in Table 2. Orange components represent Raman components for TiO_{2-x}N_x phase; (b) Structure of

MnTiO₃. Labeled oxygens form octahedra around the Ti⁴⁺ cation. O1, O2 and O3 share the plane with the MnO₆ octahedron, while O4, O5 and O6 do not (For clarity the labeling of the oxygens is the same as in [52]).

There is some discrepancy between the Raman measurements presented here and our earlier XRD measurements which showed that lamella region consists of a TiO₂ phase. The spatial resolution of the Raman measurements was 0.86 μm which is comparable with the width of the lamellas (<1 μm) so it can be expected that the sum of the Raman spectra for both phases may be obtained. Beside this, according to AFM measurements [18], the lamellas are also sometimes broken so a mixed spectrum for this region can be expected.

A low-frequency Raman line at around 100 cm⁻¹ is present for the B and C regions. The exact position of this line is difficult to pinpoint as it changes from 95 cm⁻¹ to 120 cm⁻¹ depending on the place of the measurements and additionally its relatively low intensity. To the authors' best knowledge, up to now such line was correlated with any known phonons in MnTiO₃ or TiO₂. So this low-energy phonon should be related to the vibrations of heavy ions and the reason for its appearance could be some deformations in the crystallographic lattice of the MnTiO₃ phase of the eutectic composite.

The dependences of the Raman scattering on polarization were also studied. Spectra measured for the region "C" show dependence on polarization of both incident and scattered radiation (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Polarized Raman spectra of the region “C” of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite.

The polarization dependence is most pronounced for modes related to the O-Ti-O bending motions (Fig. 6). For the sample arranged so that lamellas are parallel to Y direction (Fig. 2b) the Eg₃ mode has X polarization (Fig. 6). According to reference [52], this mode is related to the bending mode of the angles O4-Ti-O6 (Fig. 5b) where oxygens do not share the plane with the MnTiO₆ octahedron. Our earlier XRP results show that the c – axis of MnTiO₃ is parallel to the surface of the sample so the X polarization for the Eg₃ mode means that bending of the angle O4-Ti-O6 occurs mainly in the plane of the sample surface. The Ag₃ mode is related to the bending mode of angles O1-Ti-O2 (Fig. 5b) where oxygens share the plane with the MnTiO₆ octahedron. The Ag₃ Raman mode shows Y polarization which suggest that the change of the O1-Ti-O2 angle takes place in plane almost perpendicular to the sample surface.

4. Conclusions

The MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite, grown by the micro pulling-down method, consists of three distinct regions. Raman scattering studies confirmed that the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite consists of a three-dimensional network of TiO₂ elongated precipitates ellipsoidal in cross-section, interconnected by thin TiO₂ lamellas all embedded in the MnTiO₃ matrix. It was pointed out that the TiO₂ phase crystallizes in the rutile structure and MnTiO₃ matrix in the ilmenite structure. In addition, Raman studies revealed that nitrogen that was probably introduced during the growth process was mainly incorporated into the TiO₂ phase. The lamella regions exhibited Raman lines of both rutile TiO₂ and MnTiO₃ phases. This is a result of the size of the investigated area, which often combines both of these phases even when it is not seen in the optical image.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful for the “ENSEMBLE3-Center of Excellence for nanophononics, advanced materials and novel crystal growth-based technologies” project (GA No. MAB/2020/14) carried out under the International Research Agenda programs of the Foundation for Polish Science that are co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund and the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program Teaming for Excellence (GA. No. 857543) for supporting this work. The publication was created as part of the project of the Minister of Science and Higher Education "Support for the activities of Centers of Excellence established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 program" under contract No. MEiN/2023/DIR/3797. The research has been supported by a HARMONIA Project UMO-2013/10/M/ST5/00650 “Eutectics and metamaterials at a crossroads” from the National Science Center and the authors thank Dr. R. Diduszko (Lukasiewicz Research Network - Institute of Microelectronics and Photonics, Warsaw, Poland) for consulting in the crystallography field.

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A list of the Figure captions:

Fig. 1. MnO-TiO₂ system phase diagram (a), obtained samples: (b) TiO₂ crystal, (c) as-grown MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite, and (d) MnTiO₃ single crystal.

Fig. 2. Raman spectra for MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite in comparison with spectra for MnTiO₃ and TiO₂ crystals. (a) Optical image of the eutectic composite microstructure. (b) Raman spectra. (c) Raman spectral image, for TiO₂ marker at 445cm⁻¹ (green area) and for MnTiO₃ marker at 334 cm⁻¹ (red area) and 1408 cm⁻¹ (blue area).

Fig. 3. Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at the region "A" of MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. For clarity TiO_{2-x} Raman lines are plotted in orange.

Fig. 4. Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at point C for MnTiO₃ phase in MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. Calculated parameters of the deconvoluted spectrum are gathered in Table 2.

Fig. 5 (a) Fitting the Raman spectrum measured at point B (lamella region) in MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite. Calculated parameters of the deconvoluted spectrum are gathered in Table 2. Orange components represent Raman components for TiO_{2-x}N_x phase; (b) Structure of MnTiO₃. Labeled oxygens forms octahedron around the Ti⁴⁺ cation. O1, O2 and O3 share the plane with MnO₆ octahedron, while O4, O5 and O6 do not (For clarity the labeling of the oxygens is the same as in [52]).

Fig. 6. Polarized Raman spectra of the region "C" of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite.

Table 1. Calculated frequencies, ω_i , line widths, γ_i , and possible assignment of phonon modes for region "A" of MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite and rutile TiO₂ crystal.

Phonon mode	Region "A"		Rutile TiO ₂ crystal		Pure rutile TiO ₂ Ref. [53]	TiO _{2-x} N _x nanorods Ref. [54]	Assignment
	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	ω_i	
A	141.7	1.3	142.3	1.01	143	148	B _{1g}
B	232.5	43.2	235.0	39.57	236	249	two-phonon process (TPP)
C	356.4	70.2	352.8	69.76		336	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
D	444.6	20.4	443.6	20.13	447	441	E _g
E	531.4	36.4	526.9	39.39		543	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
F	610.4	22.8	609.0	22.56	612	607	A _{1g}
G	687.2	46.5	706.3	33.70		689	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
H	787.3	46.9	828.8	24.64	826		B _{2g}
I	1371.2	15.9					OH/CO/CO ₂
J	1403.1	10.1					OH/CO/CO ₂

Table 2. Calculated frequencies, ω_i , line widths, γ_i , and possible assignment of phonon modes for the regions "B" and "C" of the MnTiO₃-TiO₂ eutectic composite and for MnTiO₃ and rutile TiO₂ crystals.

Phonon mode	Region "B"		Region "C"		MnTiO ₃ single crystal		MnTiO ₃ single crystal [60]		Rutile TiO ₂ single crystal		Assignment
	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	γ_i	ω_i	ω_i	γ_i		
1	96.1	11.6	116	10.2							unknown
2	133.5	17.6	138.6	11.4							unknown
3									142.3	1.01	B _{1g} (TiO ₂)
4	161.9	17.6	164.7	8.9	164.9	2.0	168				E _{g(5)} (MnTiO ₃)
5	203.8	17.6	202.4	10.2	202.5	2.4	202				A _{g(5)} (MnTiO ₃)
6	236.4	8.0	234.6	7.8	236.6	3.1	235				E _{g(4)} (MnTiO ₃)
7	259.2	110							235.0	39.6	TPP (TiO ₂)
8	266.7	11.6	261.3	13.8	263.9	4.1	264				A _{g(4)} (MnTiO ₃)
9	335.5	17.6	334.8	12.6	334.7	5.1	335				A _{g(3)} (MnTiO ₃)
10	362.4	8.6	358.5	12.6	359.4	3.3	360				E _{g(3)} (MnTiO ₃)
11	366.9	206.1									E _(g3) (MnTiO ₃)
12	449.6	54.6	436.3	21					443.6	20.1	TiO ₂ /MnTiO ₃
13	514.0	51.6	514.6	56.0					526.9	39.4	TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
14	612.3	60.3	609.4	45.4					609.0	22.6	E _(g1) (MnTiO ₃)
15	687.7	43.9	683.5	30.8	685.0	9.3	682				A _(g1) (MnTiO ₃)
16	712	124.0									TiO _{2-x} N _x [51]
17	798.7	60.7							828.8	24.6	B _(2g) (TiO ₂)
18	958.0	5.0									OH/CO/CO ₂
19	977.0	2.8									OH/CO/CO ₂
20	1377	15.9									OH/CO/CO ₂
21	1404.5	17.9									OH/CO/CO ₂